

Balancing Home and Livelihood in traditional Meitei Society: A case study of Housewives in Wabagai Village

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Abstract—Housewives play a fundamental role in maintaining the stability and well-being of a family. Their responsibilities are extensive, spanning from household duties within the family to active roles in the social, economic, cultural, and political spheres of society. Meitei women hold a central position in the socio-economic landscape of Manipur, making vital contributions to both household stability and community development. Their economic role with various occupations for family sustenance, socio-cultural role for the maintenance of social order, response to crises, custodian to cultural practices, etc. are crucial in shaping the Meitei society. The present study is an analysis of the role and socio-economic conditions of the housewives in Wabagai village in Kakching district of Manipur. Primary data were collected to examine their demographic profile, educational status, occupation and income patterns, participation in community activities and the challenges and the psychological impact they faced during hard times. The findings of the study show that housewives contribute significantly to the socio-economic conditions of the family and society by balancing domestic responsibilities with livelihood activities such as small-scale trade, daily wage earner, weaving, market trade and agricultural work. In hard times such as the COVID-19 lockdown, they contribute greater responsibility in the family and society for which they often encountered psychological strains. The study calls for greater recognition of the role of housewives in family and society and emphasizes the need for gender parity in the working of a family.

Keywords: Challenges, COVID-19, Housewives, Meitei Society, Wabagai

I. INTRODUCTION

The worth of a civilization lies in the status and respect it accords to its women (Singh, 1998). Historically, women in India have been accorded a status below that of men. This hierarchy is closely rooted in the kinship and economic structures of India, which assign women a subordinate and secondary position within the family and, by extension, in the wider society (Chakrapani & Kumar, 1994). It is notable that demographic studies have tended to frame women's economic roles primarily in relation to fertility (Basu & Basu, 1991). However, women shoulder a much larger portion of household chores, childcare, and family caregiving. This imbalance in domestic duties significantly limits their job opportunities and even negatively impacts their overall health (Mussida & Patimo, 2021; Sharma et al., 2016). Although women's contributions to household economies remain substantial, their efforts are undervalued, particularly in agrarian and culturally stratified societies (Boserup et al., 2013).

In Meitei society, women hold a highly respected and influential position in Manipuri society. Traditionally, they have been central to the family's economic and social life. Since time immemorial, women in Manipur have been hard workers. They are mothers, wives, daughters, daughter-in-law who have to feed, nurture and take care of their children, serve husbands and in-laws. Beyond domestic roles, Meitei women are actively involved in trade, agriculture, handloom weaving, and market-based activities (Ghosh & Ghosh, 1997). The famous Ima Keithel (Mother's Market), the Asia's largest women-run market is a symbol of their economic independence and collective strength (Sudhir, 2002). Chaki-Sircar's study of Meitei women explores the viability of feminist ideals in a society shaped by strong Brahmanic and patriarchal influences. Her findings show that, despite a patrilineal structure, Meitei society is marked by notable expressions of female power and independence, making it a distinctive case within the broader Indian context (Chaki-Sircar, 1984). Meitei women have also been at the forefront of social

and political activism. Historic movements such as the Nupi Lal (Women's War) and the continuing efforts of Meira Paibis (torch bearer women) show their leadership in defending community rights, ensuring social justice, and maintaining peace and order (Sophia, 2021; Yambem, 1976; Huirem, 2024).

Although Meitei culture accords women a high status as evident in women's leadership in institutions like Ima Keithel and the historical role in movements such as the Nupi Lal, the dual burden of the housewives persists. They shoulder the primary responsibility for domestic labour, including childcare, elder care, cooking, and household management, a workload that remains largely unshared despite women's large engagement in economic activities. Even when women participate in weaving, informal trading, agriculture, and small-scale market work, their economic contributions are perceived as supplementary, and they must continue to fulfil their domestic duties too, reinforcing what Devi and Devi (2024) describe as "a simultaneous engagement in both household maintenance and livelihood support." Recent sociological and anthropological studies in Manipur confirm that the dual burden results in time-poverty, physical exhaustion, and psychosocial stress among housewives (Ngangbam, 2024), and that patriarchal household structure continue to influence decision-making, mobility, and the recognition of women's efforts despite the narratives of female empowerment (Sophia, 2021). Thus, while Meitei society is often portrayed as relatively gender-progressive, the literatures indicate that housewives continue to experience a disproportionate double workload due to the coexistence of domestic responsibilities and their essential, though undervalued, economic contributions.

The present study is an analysis of the economic activities the housewives in Wabagai village have undertaken to sustain their livelihood besides their household chores and the growing challenges they faced in hard times by taking into consideration the imposition of lockdown during COVID-19.

II. METHODOLOGY

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. The primary data was collected through structured questionnaires from 100 respondents (housewives) living in Wabagai village using random sampling technique. Census data were acquired from the online website of the Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India. The primary data collected are tabulated and descriptive statistics were used for analysis and interpretation.

III. STUDY AREA

Fig.1 Location of the study area

Wabagai is a village located in the Kakching district at a distance of 39 km to the south east from Imphal, the capital of Manipur. It extends from 24°29' N to 24° 34' N latitude and 93°53' E to 93° 57' E longitude covering an area of 980.68 hectares as shown in Fig.1. The Mayai Lambi road connects the village with Imphal. The main means of public transportation are by means of public or private bus, auto, wingers.

According to the Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India, Wabagai is inhabited by a population of 8578 out of them 4292 are male and 4286 are female as of 2011. There are 1810 households. Out of 5828 literates in the village, 2579 are female. Male literacy rate is 75.69% whereas female literacy rate is 60.17%.

IV. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS

IV.I. ECONOMIC PROFILE OF WABAGAI VILLAGE

Agriculture is the main source of economy of the village. Most of the households are engaged in agricultural activities. Various vegetables like potato, cabbage, cauliflower, mustard, beans, peas, carrots, pepper are grown in the area. The village is one of the main vegetable hubs of the state. Wabagai Lamkhai bazaar is the main market which is entirely run by women. Women sell their vegetable produces in this market mostly in the early morning and many women from other parts of the state come here and trade these vegetables to other parts of the state.

Table 1 Workers' Profile in Wabagai

Types of worker	Total	Male	Female
Total worker	4984	2485	2499
Main worker	4165	2353	1812
Main worker cultivator	3273	1781	1492
Main worker agricultural labourers	275	123	152
Main worker household industries	55	33	22
Main worker other	562	416	146
Marginal worker	819	132	687
Marginal worker cultivator	531	81	450
Marginal worker agricultural labourers	216	32	184
Marginal worker household industries	26	4	22
Marginal worker others	46	15	31
Marginal worker cultivator 3-6 months	351	44	307
Marginal worker agricultural labourers 3-6 months	178	22	156
Marginal worker household industries 3-6 months	7	1	6
Marginal worker other 3-6 months	36	15	21
Marginal worker 0-3 months	247	50	197
Marginal worker cultivator 0-3 months	180	37	143
Marginal worker agricultural labourers 0-3 months	38	10	28

Marginal worker household industries 0-3 months	19	3	16
Marginal worker other 0-3 months	10	0	10

Source – Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India

Women's active participation in all types of works and their domination in work field can easily be apprehended from [Table 1](#) which also points to the fact that in most types of works women outnumber men.

IV.II. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONTRIBUTION OF WOMEN

The intensity of hard work and responsibility a housewife carries to maintain her family is really enormous and commendable too. Moreover, they also try to contribute to the socio-economic well being of the locality whatever little it might be. Women here indulge in small saving activities not for personal family needs but for the need of the whole leikai (locality). E.g. thasi-purnima marup (thasi means new moon, purnima means full moon) has almost become a tradition for some leikais. It is a small saving act done exclusively by women every full moon and new moon day. On these particular days, women of each household will come out in the night and contribute a very small sum of rupees like 10 or 20. This sum of rupees will be saved overtime may be one or two years for future use of the leikai. For this purpose they choose night time for they cannot spare their busy day time.

IV.III. WOMEN IN SOCIAL ISSUES

The ability of the Meitei women in terms of their resilience, organisational capacity and strong participation in economic and social issues are well manifested in the women living in Wabagai too. Not only attending to the household chores and socio-economic needs, they are also engaged in social issues of local and state importance like cases of human right violation, drug abuse, human trafficking. Every leikai in the valley of Manipur has meira paibis (torch bearers). These torches are usually made of bamboos with kerosene inside. As Manipur is in an arms conflict zone there are frequent cases of human right violation. Whenever any such cases happen, without any instigation women will come out of their comfortable homes in the night bearing torches and try to save the victim at their best. Moreover they would also stage protests in the form of rallies.

V. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The findings of this study reveal that the housewives of Wabagai perform a multidimensional set of roles that extend far beyond conventional domestic responsibilities. Their everyday activities reflect the village's socio-economic dynamics, livelihood systems, and spatial patterns of work and mobility. The analysis shows that women contribute significantly to household income through involvement in cultivation, daily wage earning, small scale trade, weaving, etc. The findings have been shown in [Table 2](#).

Table 2 General information about the Respondents (Housewives)

Sl. No.	Items	Categories	Frequency (N)=100
1	Family size	Small (1 - 4)	44
		Medium (5 - 8)	56
2	Age (in years)	20-30	26
		31-40	28
		41-50	30
		Above 50	16
3	Occupations	Farmer/cultivator	36

		Daily wage earner	20
		Small scale trader	12
		Weaver	22
		Not specific	10
4	Education	Illiterate	20
		8 th Passed	23
		10 th Passed	29
		12 th passed	17
		Graduate	11
5	Income	Below 10000	20
		10000-30000	66
		Above 30000	14

V.I. FAMILY SIZE

The findings of the household survey reveals that 44% of the households have a family size of 1-4 persons and the rest of the 56% of the households have a family size of 5-8 persons. Fig.2 shows that 26% of the housewives surveyed belong to the age group 20-30, 28% belong to the age group 31-40, 30% belong to the age group 41-50 and 16% belong to the age group above 50.

Fig.2 Number of housewives in each Age Category

V.II. OCCUPATIONS

The housewives in Wabagai are engaged in diversified economic activities beyond their domestic responsibilities. A significant proportion of 36% of them are involved in farming and cultivation, indicating that agriculture remains the primary livelihood backbone of the village (Fig.3). Weaving (22%) constitutes the second highest occupation of the housewives which highlights the continued relevance of traditional weaving among Meitei women. Weaving is not only culturally embedded but also serves as a flexible home-based income source that can be done besides the household duties. 20% of the housewives work as daily wage earners. The participation of women as daily wage earners reflects not only their economic necessity but also their

capability and resilience in contributing to the household income. Another 12% of the housewives are small-scale traders, involved in selling vegetables, homemade products and handloom items. Their participation shows the continuation of a strong women-led market tradition, where economic activity is closely linked to their social identity and community life. The remaining 10% fall under not specific, representing women who either work irregularly, have multiple shifting occupations, or are not engaged in income-generating work at the moment.

Fig.3 Frequency of different occupations of the housewives

V.III. EDUCATION

The educational profile of the housewives shows a moderate level of schooling. 80% of the housewives have access to education while the remaining 20% are illiterate. 23% of the housewives have passed the 8th standard while 29% of them have passed the 10th standard. Housewives who have passed the 12th standard constitute 17% while housewives who have graduated constitute 11%. The statistics show that housewives in the Wabagai village have an acceptable level of access to the basic formal education as seen in Fig. 4.

Fig.4 Educational Attainment of the housewives in Wabagai village

V.IV. INCOME

For the survey, the income of the housewives was divided into three categories i.e. below 10000, 10000-30000 and above 30000 as seen in Fig.5. The data shows a high concentration of the income of the housewives in the lower to middle income group, indicating that the housewives earn a moderate income besides the household chores. 20% of the respondents (housewives) fall in the lowest income group i.e. below 10000. This suggests that the housewives have limited access to stable

or well-paid work. 66% of the housewives earn a monthly income within the range of 10000-30000. It shows that the majority of housewives contribute a moderate but steady income in the running of the family possibly through small businesses, weaving, trading, or agricultural works. A small proportion of housewives (14%) fall in the higher income group i.e. above 30000. This suggests that some of the housewives, in their way to search for a modest income to support the family, have already set up a mechanism to earn a significant amount of income possibly through small business and entrepreneurial networks. Although the income structure is skewed towards the lower and middle income group, the findings of the study reveal that the housewives in the Wabagai village contribute a moderate but critical income and help sustain the family needs.

Fig.5 Income level of the housewives in the Wabagai village

V.V. HUSBAND’S NATURE

Usually husband’s nature in a family reflects a complex interplay of support, neutrality, and abusive characters shaped by cultural expectations, household responsibilities and the behaviour of the husband himself. In many families, husbands continue to uphold traditional roles as primary decision-makers, while housewives manage the domestic and household caregiving tasks. At the same time, the presence of husbands who are intoxicant do often show either abusive behaviour or are non cooperative in the earning activities and sustaining the family. In such cases, women, especially the housewives in the family, suffer and had to manage both the household chores and the earning activities to sustain the family. Two sets of data have also been collected related to the husband’s nature in Wabagai village to understand better the housewives’ role and burden in the family which are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3 Husbands’ Nature

Sl no.	Items	Categories	Frequency (N=100)
1	Reflection on husband	Supportive to household chores	30
		Neutral	58
		Abusive	12
2	Husband is an intoxicant (alcohol, tobacco, khaini user)	Yes	56
		No	44

Two sets of data have been collected for the analysis of the husband's nature. The first one is the reflection on husband where three variables i.e. supportive nature, neutral and abusive nature of husbands have been considered. The second set of data deals with the intoxication of the husbands. The findings of the study reveals that 30% of the husbands are supportive to household chores whereas 58% of the husbands are neutral in character which means they are neither supporting the household chores nor are abusive in behaviour too. A small section of the husbands (12%) are abusive in behaviour. As many as 56% of the husbands surveyed are intoxicants which means they are either alcohol, tobacco or khaini user. And the remaining 44% are non-intoxicant which means they don't use any of the intoxicants.

V.VI. HOUSEWIVES' ROLE IN HARD TIMES

Meitei women have historically shown remarkable resilience during periods of crisis, whether caused by conflict, economic hardship, or public health emergencies like COVID-19. Their ability to balance domestic responsibilities with economic and emotional support highlights their central role in keeping Meitei society functioning in moments of stress and instability. Here, a particular situation of hard time i.e. COVID-19 is considered for the assessment of the challenging roles played by the housewives and the psychological impact on them in Wabagai village at the family and community level.

During the strict lockdown due to COVID-19 pandemic, there is a marked change in the income structure of the families. Those who belong to the income group within 30,000 per month are largely affected whereas those belonging to higher income group of above 30,000 remain least affected as they have a stable income. On the whole 86% of the families have been severely affected by the lockdown to such an extent that 40% of them report to have no income at all during the lockdown.

Table 4 Increase in the Number of Women Breadwinners during the Lockdown

Sl no	Items	Categories	Frequency (N=100)
1	Main breadwinners of the family before lockdown	Husband	48
		Housewife	8
		Both	40
		Others	4
2	Main breadwinners of the family during lockdown	Husband	30
		Housewife	48
		Both	18
		Others	4

A paradigm shift is obviously observed in the Table 4 and Fig.6 when women take the lead role in the maintenance of their families during the lockdown. Usually it is the men who are the main bread winners of families. But during the lockdown women come forward to anyhow maintain the family needs. Thus 48% of the women become lone breadwinners during the lockdown against 8% before the lockdown. It is because during lockdown all earning activities are shut down except selling vegetable, and shops of groceries and pharmacy. One point to be noted is that selling vegetable is usually considered to be women's job. During the pandemic, women coming out searching for a means of earning give way to the rise of the number of women as main breadwinners.

For women belonging to very low income group, their hardship is beyond imagination. Their main problem is finding a means of earning. Though, they do get free rice supplied by government, it is not enough. Moreover, they need money to maintain

their families and attend to various family needs. Some of such women come out unafraid of the pandemic and do trading of vegetables here and there openly or sometimes covertly to evade strict lockdown security.

Fig.6 Changing role of housewives in the family before and after the lockdown

The pandemic has made gender disparity more obvious. For most men, lockdown becomes lockdown of most of their activities. But for women, it means increase in responsibilities as the lockdown does not include household chores. The problem is aggravated when husbands use intoxicants like alcohol, tobacco products, khaini as 56% of the husbands are reported to be intoxicant users. It also contributes to the economic, psychological and physical challenges faced by women during the pandemic lockdown.

Table 5 Psychological Impact of COVID-19 on Housewives

Sl no.	Items	Categories	Frequency (N=100)	Percentage
1	Most challenging during the lockdown	Fear of the pandemic	44	44
		Getting a means of earning	28	28
		Taking care of children	18	18
		Problem created by intoxicant husband	4	4
		Others	0	0
2	Mental state during the lockdown	Anger/depression/insomnia/stress	94	94
		No problem	6	6
3	Need for psychological support	Yes	78	78
		No	22	22

The report that 44% of the housewives take their fear for the pandemic as the greatest challenge they face during the lockdown points to the extent which the pandemic has psychologically affected them (Table 5). The gravity of the fear has reached to

such a point that only 28% of women report finding a means of earning is their greatest challenge during the lockdown. As many as 94% of housewives under study report to have suffered from mental unrest like anger, depression and insomnia and 78% of them claim that they need psychological support during the lockdown. Pandemic induced economic unrest combined with the fear for the invading pandemic brings tremendous economical, social and psychological impact on the people especially women.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study of housewives in Wabagai highlights the significant yet often undervalued role that women play in sustaining household and community life in the Meitei society. The housewives in Wabagai took multiple responsibilities from managing household chores to supporting family livelihoods through involvement in agriculture, small trading, and informal work. The behaviour of the husbands really makes difference in the role and the burden carried by the housewives. The presence of a major portion of unsupportive husbands to household chores adds to the challenges of the housewives. Despite these challenges, the Meitei women in general, and the housewives of Wabagai in particular, have the will power and the guts to carry the family responsibilities single-handedly even when she doesn't get the support of her husband. The role of housewives in a family and the society became more pronounced during hard times. Their resilience and adaptability particularly during hard times such as the COVID-19 lockdown, reflects their crucial contribution to the social and economic stability of the family and the society. Overall, the study underscores the need to acknowledge the housewives as an equally important contributor to the family and to encourage greater gender-equitable practices in a family to support their well being.

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